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Supporting Information S1 for *Geophysical Research Letters*

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**~550-Year Climate Periodicity in the Yunnan-Guizhou Plateau during the late
Mid-Holocene: Insights and Implications**

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24 **Introduction**

25 The [Supporting Information S1](#) provided includes details on the methods of all the
26 lab work ([Text S1](#)), the results of the trace elements ([Text S1](#)), the demonstration of
27 annual lamina ([Text S2](#)) and application of least-squares fit ([Text S2](#)), the methods
28 and the results of summed ^{14}C probability (SCP) distributions in southwestern China
29 ([Text S3](#)) and a discussion on how ENSO and local precipitation can influence the
30 proxies ([Text S4](#)). Additionally, there are supporting figures ([Figure S1 to S8](#)) for the
31 main text and the data on ^{230}Th dating ([Table S1](#)) in this file.

32

33 **Text S1. Lab work methods and the results of trace elements**

34

35 ^{230}Th dating method

36 Total 16 ^{230}Th dating subsamples (~40–60 mg for each) were extracted using a dental
37 drill with a 0.9 mm burr. The subsamples were dated at Xi'an Jiaotong University
38 using a Thermo-Finnigan Neptune-plus multicollector inductively coupled plasma
39 mass spectrometer (MC-ICP-MS). Standard chemistry procedures ([Edwards et al.,
40 1987](#)) were used to separate uranium and thorium. A triple-spike (^{229}Th - ^{233}U - ^{236}U) was
41 employed to correct instrumental fractionation and determine U-Th isotopic ratios
42 and concentrations. The instrumentation, standardization, and half-lives were
43 reported in [Cheng et al. \(2000, 2013\)](#). We followed the similar procedures to
44 characterize the multiplier as described in [Cheng et al. \(2000\)](#). Uncertainties were
45 calculated offline at 2σ level, including corrections for blanks, multiplier dark noise,
46 abundance sensitivity, and contents of the same nuclides in the spike solution.
47 Corrected ^{230}Th ages ([Table S1](#)) assume an initial $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}$ atomic ratio of 4.4 ± 2.2
48 $\times 10^{-6}$ and a bulk earth $^{232}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$ value of 3.8 for material at secular equilibrium
49 ([Cheng et al., 2013](#)).

50 **Stable isotope analysis method**

51 An automated triaxial micro mill (Sherline 8540 CNC Mill) was used to obtain
52 subsamples for stable isotopic analyses. Along the growth axis (14.25–351.75 mm
53 from the top), 0.25mm increments milling were implemented, and 1342 subsamples
54 were obtained. Stable isotope measurements were performed on a Finnigan Delta V
55 PLUS Isotope Mass Spectrometer coupled to an automated carbonate preparation
56 system (Gasbench II) at the Department of Environmental Sciences, University of
57 Basel. The precision (1σ) of both instruments is $\leq 0.08\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. Isotope
58 values are reported relative to the Vienna Peedee Belemnite (VPDB) standard ([Table
59 S2](#)).

60 **Methods and results of trace elements analysis**

61 To test the prior calcite precipitation (PCP) and/or water-rock reaction processes
62 influences, 1117 trace element data (Mg/Ca and Sr/Ca) were measured by laser-
63 induced break-down spectroscopy system at Isotope Laboratory, Xi'an Jiaotong
64 University. The track of the trace element analysis parallels to stable isotope's track
65 (Figure S2), with 0.3mm increments between analysis points. An yttrium-aluminum-
66 garnet-Nd laser (Beamtech, Dawa-200) was used to generate a 1064-nm laser using a
67 lens focusing the 5-mm beam diameter to 0.1mm (H. Li et al., 2020). Emitted plasma
68 from the sample surface was collected by optical fibers and sent to a four-passage
69 spectrometer (Ocean Optics MX500+). Mg (I, 279.6 nm), Sr (II, 407.9 nm), and Ca (II,
70 373.7 nm) signals were collected respectively. Time series of Mg/Ca and Sr/Ca were
71 obtained by averaging ratios of 20 laser shots at each subsample position after five
72 cleaning shots. This method allows for the semiquantitative measurement of Mg/Ca
73 and Sr/Ca values by selecting Ca as an internal standard to cancel out any errors that
74 may arise due to changes in operating conditions (H. Li et al., 2018). Although the
75 trace element data in our study were not analyzed using a standard due to the
76 relatively unimportant nature of their absolute values, this did not hinder our ability
77 to semiquantitative analyze their long-term patterns (e.g., H. Li et al., 2018, 2020).

78 The results of Mg/Ca and Sr/Ca showed a similar pattern between each other, with a
79 high value during the mid-Holocene and a low value during the late-Holocene.
80 Significantly positive correlations are observed between Mg/Ca and Sr/Ca records,
81 with a correlation of 0.38 and significance at 99.9% level (Figure S3), suggesting PCP
82 and/or water-rock processes is the main consideration controlling both trend
83 (Fairchild & Treble, 2009; Johnson et al., 2006; McMillan et al., 2005).

84 **Methods of Fluorescence images**

85 The sample GZXND21-1 was cut into 7 flat sections, and further polished using
86 abrasive resin. The lamina images were obtained in the State Key Laboratory for
87 Manufacturing Systems Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong University, using a confocal laser
88 fluorescent microscopy (CLFM, Nikon A1-1024) with a 40-mW and 488-nm laser line
89 (Zhao & Cheng, 2017). 19 images were attained at high resolution and merged
90 together for the whole-sample lamina counting.

91 **Text S2. Demonstration of annual lamina and application of least-squares fit**

92 In order to construct a precise floating lamina chronology (counting chronology), the
93 annual nature of the laminae needs to be established. This can be achieved by
94 comparing the number of laminae counted between absolutely-dated ages. Our
95 speleothem sample GZXND21-1 has clear lamina bands under CLFM (Figure S2).
96 Following W. Y. Li et al. (2022), lamina counting was repeated a total of five times,
97 with the thickness of the laminae being measured during the first count. The results
98 show that the laminae are continuous, and the number of paired laminae between
99 two consecutive ^{230}Th dates matches with the ^{230}Th age difference within uncertainty

100 (Figure S2). This agreement supports our interpretation that the laminae are annual
101 (Tan et al., 2006) and thus allows constructing a precise age model (Domínguez-Villar
102 et al., 2012).

103 Age models for our annually laminated speleothem GZXND21-1 was reconstructed
104 using the floating lamina chronology anchored by 16 high-precision ^{230}Th dates
105 (Figure S2), using the least-squares fitting method to get the best fit of the ^{230}Th
106 dates to the floating lamina chronology (Domínguez-Villar et al., 2012). The age
107 model has an estimated maximum age uncertainty of ± 26 yrs (2σ). The uncertainty of
108 the age model (26 yrs) constructed using the method considered counting
109 uncertainty (25 yrs) and the uncertainty when anchoring the floating lamina
110 chronology to the absolutely-dated ^{230}Th dates (7.5 yrs) (Domínguez-Villar et al.,
111 2012).

112 **Text S3. Methods and results of reconstructing summed ^{14}C probability** 113 **distributions (SCP)**

114 Existing research has established that human occupation contributes to the
115 production and deposition of larger amounts of cultural carbon (Surovell et al., 2009;
116 Williams, 2012). When the deposited carbon is well-preserved, archaeologists are
117 able to recover more carbon, and this recovery is further enhanced by thorough
118 archaeological investigations, which also increase the retrieval of dating samples
119 (Surovell et al., 2009; Williams, 2012). Consequently, the abundance of radiocarbon
120 dates could potentially serve as a proxy for human population in a region during a
121 specific time frame (Surovell et al., 2009; Williams, 2012). Nevertheless,
122 archaeologists encounter challenges regarding the validity of employing "dates as
123 data" in the context of archaeological ^{14}C dates. The term "dates as data" refers to the
124 practice of using ^{14}C dates as a data source, which is presumed to represent
125 spatiotemporal shifts in paleodemography (e.g., C. Wang et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2019).
126 Thus, verifying this assumption may prove difficult (e.g., Chaput & Gajewski, 2016),
127 and it encompasses biases and errors related to archaeological studies, such as
128 taphonomic loss of samples and variable sample sizes (e.g., Surovell et al., 2009), as
129 well as issues arising from the analysis of databases for the sites under investigation.
130 These problems can be traced back to quality concerns, sample size, sampling bias,
131 temporal bias, taphonomic issues, and human factors (e.g., Brown, 2015; Surovell &
132 Brantingham, 2007). Despite the influence of these issues on archaeological
133 radiocarbon dates, several noteworthy studies in China have attempted to minimize
134 bias by employing specific statistical approaches (e.g., C. Wang et al., 2014; Xu et al.,
135 2019). By applying the methods suggested by C. Wang et al. (2014) and Xu et al.
136 (2019), we reconstruct the combined ^{14}C probability records in southwestern China,
137 allowing us to further explore population variations within this region.

138 (1) Williams (2012) highlights that a sufficiently extensive regional sample set, derived
139 from a large collection of sites, can be considered a quasi-random sample set without

140 site and period-level biases. Consequently, it can be assumed to provide a statistically
141 reliable basis for a robust SCP distribution that reflects true population trends. As a
142 result, it is crucial for archaeologists to gather ample samples to minimize sampling
143 bias. The underlying assumption of SCP analysis is that a large enough sample of
144 radiocarbon dates from an adequately extensive area will serve as valid evidence for
145 indicating population fluctuations (e.g., [Gamble et al., 2005](#); [Shennan & Edinborough,
146 2007](#); [Williams, 2012](#)). In terms of statistics, [Michczyńska and Pazdur \(2004\)](#) applied
147 Monte Carlo techniques to an artificial dataset, showing that the minimum number of
148 radiocarbon dates required (in order to keep statistical fluctuations below 50%)
149 depends on the mean of the standard deviations reported for radiocarbon dates in
150 the sample (laboratory error) (ΔT) and the length of the time series. For instance,
151 when considering a time interval of 0–14.0 kyrs and $\Delta T = 115$ yrs, at least 200 dates
152 are necessary. [Williams \(2012\)](#) re-sampled AustArch datasets to determine the
153 minimum number of dates needed for reliable SCP plots, the results indicate that
154 fewer than 200–500 radiocarbon dates should be considered provisional.

155 Considering the limitation of published ^{14}C dates in Yunnan-Guizhou Plateau (YGP),
156 we have incorporated data from the Sichuan and Chongqing regions in our analysis
157 to increase the sample size. Similar with YGP, these regions shown similar close living
158 environments (which resulted in a cultural lag of several thousand years than eastern
159 China, e.g., [Chen, 2020](#)) as well as the parallel hunter-fisher-gatherer lifestyles before
160 the first cold event during 5500–5000 yrs BP (e.g., [Jin et al., 2014](#)). We re-selected ^{14}C
161 dates from integrated database of archaeological radiocarbon dates for China ([C.
162 Wang et al., 2014](#)). This database included 4656 published archaeological ^{14}C
163 datasets. We assembled 325 archaeological ^{14}C dates to build a dataset for
164 southwestern China, among which 292 dates were extracted from the database for
165 China ([C. Wang et al., 2014](#)) and 33 dates were from new publications ([Table S3](#)). Over
166 95% ($n = 319$) of the dates have errors of 400 yrs or less, and over 95% ($n = 310$) of
167 the dates were aged before than 14 kyr BP. Following [Williams \(2012\)](#), we report that
168 the mean standard deviation (ΔT) for the entire sample set was 107.7 yrs. Relevant
169 information about the dating methods and materials used in the database, which are
170 significant for evaluating dating reliability, are summarized ([Table S3](#)).

171 (2) We excluded 61 ^{14}C dates attributes: (i) Dates characterized by substantial
172 uncertainty (1σ standard deviation exceeding 400 ^{14}C years); (ii) dates obtained from
173 shells, soils, unidentified substances, or other materials deemed unsuitable for dating
174 purposes; and (iii) dates originating from sites or objects with tenuous connections to
175 human habitation or settlements, including ancient temples, pagodas, or canoes. In
176 instances where dates were obtained from multiple sample materials (such as
177 charcoal and shell, or charcoal and charred millet seed) found in the same context,
178 the most reliable dating material was selected. Consequently, the assembled
179 database comprised 264 dates, and ΔT was reduced to 85.6.

180 (3) After filtering out unsuitable data, we employed the R_Combine command in
181 OxCal v4.4 to consolidate redundant dates. This approach offers two benefits: (i) it
182 lowers the standard deviation and enhances the accuracy of each site's temporal
183 assignment; and (ii) it minimizes sampling bias introduced by sites or phases with
184 numerous radiocarbon dates during statistical analyses. If a date is very similar to
185 others at the same archaeological site, the method combines these dates to generate
186 a new date. This procedure diminishes the weighting of sites or phases with many
187 dates: for instance, the number of dates from the Sanxingdui site decreases from 23
188 to 8, reducing its frequency in the total sample set from 9% to 3% (refer to [Table S4](#)).

189 (4) All the ^{14}C dates were calibrated using standard techniques and software. They are
190 reported in years before present (BP, before present = 1950 CE) and are based on the
191 Libby half-life of 5568 years with 1σ standard deviation. Calibration was performed
192 using the OxCal 4.4 program and IntCal20 curve, with ranges expressed at both 1σ
193 (68.2%) and 2σ (95.4%) confidence levels. All calibrated ages reported are referred to
194 as "cal yrs BP".

195 (5) We calibrated averaged dates (95.4% confidence) and generated SCP values for
196 the regions of southwestern China using the Sum function in the OxCal 4.4 program
197 and the IntCal20 calibration curve. Additionally, we applied the empirical model
198 proposed by [Surovell et al. \(2009\)](#) to correct for taphonomic bias, as it is assumed
199 that older dates might be underestimated due to natural destructive processes.

200 (6) After correction, the data were standardized (normalized) using the following
201 formula: X_i/X_{\max} , where X_i represents each individual value and X_{\max} is the maximum
202 value in the series ([Table S5](#)).

203 The results of the SCP indicate that the population in southwestern China was
204 relatively low between 10000–6000 yrs BP. From 5700–4800 yrs BP, the population
205 experienced an overall increase, which aligns with previously published results from
206 the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau ([C. Wang et al., 2014](#)). This population growth may be
207 attributed to the favorable Mid-Holocene climate ([Qi et al., 2013](#); [C. Wang et al.,](#)
208 [2014](#)). Among these periods, during 5500–5000 yrs BP, the population experienced a
209 significant decrease, which is consistent with the cold climate states recorded by our
210 PC1 data ([Figure 3](#)), suggest that the potential environmental degradation limited the
211 growth of prehistoric populations.

212

213 **Text S4. Influence of ENSO and local precipitation on proxies**

214 The precipitation variations in the cave area are typical in southwestern China, which
215 is strongly influenced by the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) ([Figure 1](#) and [Figure](#)
216 [S1b](#)). During El Niño years, weak convection and decreased rainfall in the western
217 North Pacific often leads to a positive-negative-positive Rossby wave train

218 accompanied by a negative phase of the East Asian Pattern (EAP), resulting in the
219 southward extension of the western Pacific subtropical high (WPSH) and increased
220 Meiyu rainfall in the middle and lower Yangtze River Valley (Figure S1b and e.g.,
221 Kosaka et al., 2012; Nitta, 1987; H. Zhang et al., 2021; J. Zhang et al. 2021).

222 Previous studies also have shown that the ENSO is a crucial factor in controlling
223 rainfall variations in the middle and lower reaches of the Yangtze River (including our
224 research area and Heshang Cave) on a multi-centennial timescale (Zhu et al., 2017; J.
225 Zhang et al., 2021). The correlation map (Figure 1a) shows a significant positive
226 correlation of precipitation between these regions, where a positive precipitation
227 anomaly also coincided during the El Niño years (Figure S1). A close comparison
228 between our PC1 data and the Heshang Cave $IRM_{\text{soft-flux}}$ record (a local rainfall proxy
229 influenced by ENSO on a multi-centennial timescale), however, does not show an in-
230 phase relationship on a multi-centennial timescale (Figure S8), likely implying a
231 relatively weak influence of rainfall and ENSO on GZXND21-1 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina
232 thickness records on a multi-centennial timescale. Multiple lines of modern
233 observational evidence further support this hypothesis, including the significant
234 uniformity in temperature variations in China (e.g., Figure 1; Ren et al., 2017) and the
235 weak influence of rainfall on biomass in southwestern China (e.g., H. Liu et al., 2018; S.
236 Tao et al., 2022; J. Wang et al., 2015). This phenomenon may result from the fact that
237 in our research area, rainfall is always sufficient, leaving temperature as the major
238 limiting factor for vegetation and edaphon growth (e.g., Folmeister et al., 2020; Huo
239 & Sun, 2021).

240

241

242 **Figure S1** Meteorological data and the influence of ENSO. Meteorological data are
 243 from the National Meteorological Data Center
 244 (www.nmic.cn/data/cdcdetail/dataCode/SURF_CLI_CHN_MUL_MMON_19812010.html
 245). (a) Monthly precipitation and temperature (1981-2010 CE). (b) MJJAS rainfall
 246 anomalies during the decaying phase of the 1982/1983, 1987/1988, 1992/1993,
 247 1997/1998 and 2006/2007 El Niño events. Precipitation data are obtained from the
 248 Climatic Research Unit (CRU TS v4.05, [Harris et al., 2020](#)) with a grid resolution of 0.5
 249 × 0.5°. Also shown are the locations of climate archives in monsoonal China, the red
 250 star, the yellow dot, and the blue dot mark our site, Heshang cave, and lake
 251 Xiaolongwan, respectively.

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256 **Figure S2** Polished slab of sample GZXND21-1, its confocal laser fluorescent
 257 microscopy images and age model. The black arrow lines on the polished sample slab
 258 mark the stable isotope subsample track. The age model was reconstructed using the
 259 method of least-squares fitting of the lamina counting to the ^{230}Th dates
 260 (Dominguez-Villar et al., 2012) (see Text S2). Error bars are 2-sigma dating error. The
 261 blue background marks the uncertainty of the Copra-based age model (Breitenbach
 262 et al., 2012). The reference of sample growth rate (the slope of the lines in the circle)
 263 is shown at down left.

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269 **Figure S3** The scatter diagram of Sr/Ca vs. Mg/Ca. Their Pearson correlation
 270 coefficient and p value are marked down right.

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274 **Figure S4** Time series of GZXND21-1 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina thickness, and their
 275 periodicities. (a) The NGRIP ice core $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record from Greenland (blue, [Rasmussen et](#)
 276 [al., 2014](#)) and PC1 results of GZXND21-1 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina thickness (orange, this
 277 study). (b) The PC1 result from both $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina thickness (this study). (c) The
 278 GZXND21-1 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ record (this study). (d) The GZXND21-1 lamina thickness (thin line)
 279 and its 10-point average (thick line) records (this study). (e) and (f) Power spectrum
 280 analyses of GZXND21-1 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina thickness. The areas upper than the thick
 281 purple line mark the 95% significance level. (g) Results of cross-wavelet analysis of
 282 the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina thickness records, calculated using the Acycle package ([M. Li et](#)
 283 [al., 2019](#)). The black arrows (right/left) indicate the two records' phase relationship
 284 (in/anti-phased). The areas inside the thick line mark the 95% significance level.

285

286 **Figure S5** Principal components analysis (PCA) loading plot. The PCA loading plot
 287 showcases the outcomes of the principal components analysis conducted on the
 288 standardized $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina thickness data. The analysis aims to determine the
 289 primary gradients related to vegetation and temperature variations. The first and the
 290 second principal components (PC1 and PC2) explain 57% and 43% of the total
 291 variance, with respective eigenvalues of 1.14 and 0.86. On PC1, both $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and lamina
 292 thickness contribute equally with a 50% contribution each. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data exhibited
 293 positive loadings on the PC1 axis, while lamina thickness data showed negative
 294 loadings. The multi-centennial variations of PC1 demonstrate clear correlations with
 295 the original GXZND21-1 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, lamina thickness record, and Greenland ice core $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
 296 data (Figure S4). This suggests that the PC1 data can effectively represent
 297 temperature and vegetation changes on multi-centennial scale. Consequently, the
 298 PC1 loadings ranging from warm climates with abundant vegetation (negative PC1)
 299 to colder climates with reduced vegetation (positive PC1).

300

301

302 **Figure S6** Results of 400-600 band-pass (B.P.400-600) filtering. (a) Filtered (green) and
 303 original (light green) $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ results, (b) filtered (blue) and original (light blue) PC1
 304 results, (c) filtered (purple) and original (light purple) PC1 results. The arrows and

305 numbers indicate the interval between adjacent peaks. All data presented are derived
306 from this study.
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308

309 **Figure S7** Power spectrum analyses of the GZXND21-1 (a) Mg/Ca, (b) Sr/Ca, (c) $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
310 and (d) PC1 results, all the data derived from this study. The areas upper than the
311 thick purple line mark the 95% significance level.

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316 **Figure S8** Comparison of the PC1 results with meteorological data. (a) GXND21-1
 317 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ results (this study). (b) Heshang cave IRMsoft-flux records (Zhu et al., 2017). (c)
 318 GXND21-1 PC1 results (this study). (d) and (e) GXND21-1 Sr/Ca (d) and Mg/Ca (e)
 319 results (this study).

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Table S1 ²³⁰Th dating results. The error is 2σ error.

Sample	²³⁸ U		²³² Th		²³⁰ Th / ²³² Th		δ ²³⁴ U*		²³⁰ Th / ²³⁸ U		²³⁰ Th Age (y)		²³⁰ Th Age (y)		δ ²³⁴ U _{initial} **		²³⁰ Th Age (y BP [#])	
Number	(ppb)		(ppt)		(atomic x10 ⁻⁶)		(measured)		(activity)		(uncorrected)		(corrected)		(corrected)		(corrected)	
GZXND21-1-14	481.5	±1.6	50	±3	17023	±872	2163.4	±7.0	0.1067	±0.0005	3729	±20	3728	±20	2186	±7	3659	±20
GZXND21-1-35	467.8	±0.5	40	±1	21415	±663	2153.6	±2.6	0.1106	±0.0003	3877	±10	3876	±10	2177	±3	3805	±10
GZXND21-1-59	413.5	±1.6	122	±3	6302	±170	2131.6	±8.3	0.1129	±0.0006	3990	±24	3987	±24	2156	±8	3916	±24
GZXND21-1-111	383.0	±0.4	25	±2	31427	±2346	2121.0	±2.5	0.1239	±0.0006	4398	±21	4397	±21	2147	±2	4326	±21
GZXND21-1-135	616.3	±0.7	43	±2	29981	±1184	2132.5	±3.0	0.1267	±0.0004	4482	±15	4482	±15	2160	±3	4411	±15
GZXND21-1-151	651.3	±0.5	46	±2	31959	±1498	2302.6	±2.5	0.1374	±0.0004	4613	±13	4612	±13	2333	±3	4541	±13
GZXND21-1-176	529.4	±0.5	28	±1	43729	±1959	2170.7	±2.5	0.1381	±0.0003	4833	±12	4832	±12	2200	±3	4761	±12
GZXND21-1-182	466.5	±0.5	74	±3	14574	±500	2200.2	±3.0	0.1409	±0.0005	4887	±17	4885	±17	2231	±3	4814	±17
GZXND21-1-193	426.0	±0.4	63	±2	15849	±555	2179.0	±2.5	0.1417	±0.0004	4949	±15	4947	±15	2210	±3	4876	±15
GZXND21-1-219	461.2	±0.6	125	±4	8796	±263	2150.5	±3.7	0.1452	±0.0008	5118	±28	5115	±28	2182	±4	5044	±28
GZXND21-1-229	497.3	±0.5	101	±2	11819	±280	2130.0	±2.7	0.1462	±0.0004	5191	±15	5189	±15	2161	±3	5118	±15
GZXND21-1-248	434.2	±0.4	101	±3	10581	±345	2132.5	±2.7	0.1500	±0.0005	5321	±20	5319	±20	2165	±3	5248	±20
GZXND21-1-276	409.5	±0.5	59	±2	17918	±607	2178.3	±3.2	0.1567	±0.0005	5484	±18	5483	±18	2212	±3	5412	±18
GZXND21-1-298	359.6	±0.4	182	±4	5319	±132	2252.8	±3.5	0.1635	±0.0006	5591	±23	5586	±24	2289	±4	5515	±24
GZXND21-1-321	459.6	±0.6	62	±2	20466	±688	2240.6	±3.4	0.1662	±0.0005	5708	±18	5707	±18	2277	±3	5636	±18
GZXND21-1-350	353.6	±0.3	100	±3	10014	±352	2217.7	±2.9	0.1715	±0.0007	5938	±25	5935	±25	2255	±3	5864	±25

U decay constants: $\lambda_{238} = 1.55125 \times 10^{-10}$ (Jaffey et al., 1971) and $\lambda_{234} = 2.82206 \times 10^{-6}$ (Cheng et al., 2013). Th decay constant: $\lambda_{230} = 9.1705 \times 10^{-6}$ (Cheng et al., 2013).

* $\delta^{234}\text{U} = ([^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}]_{\text{activity}} - 1) \times 1000$. ** $\delta^{234}\text{U}_{\text{initial}}$ was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., $\delta^{234}\text{U}_{\text{initial}} = d^{234}\text{U}_{\text{measured}} \times e^{\lambda_{234} \times T}$.

Corrected ²³⁰Th ages assume the initial ²³⁰Th/²³²Th atomic ratio of $4.4 \pm 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$.

Those are the values for a material at secular equilibrium, with the bulk earth ²³²Th/²³⁸U value of 3.8. The errors are arbitrarily assumed to be 50%.

BP stands for "Before Present" where the "Present" is defined as the year 1950 A.D.

